

MIDDLE POWER DIPLOMACY IN THE INDO-PACIFIC: ASSESSING AUSTRALIA'S STRATEGIC BALANCING BETWEEN SECURITY ALLIANCES AND ECONOMIC PARTNERSHIPS

*Aadil Bashir Parry**

Abstract

The Indo-Pacific has become the most strategically contested region of the twenty-first century, shaped by the growing rivalry between the United States and China. In such an environment, middle powers have acquired renewed significance as they seek to safeguard their interests without directly challenging or aligning fully with great powers. This paper examines Australia's foreign policy as a leading example of middle power diplomacy in the Indo-Pacific. It investigates the structural dilemma created by Australia's dependence on the United States for security and its reliance on China for economic growth. Drawing on theoretical debates on middle power behaviour, the study analyses Australia's evolving diplomatic strategies, including its participation in AUKUS and the Quad, and its diversification through closer engagement with India, Japan and ASEAN. The paper argues that while Australia continues to project itself as a middle power through multilateralism, coalition-building and norm entrepreneurship, its autonomy is significantly constrained by asymmetric interdependence. The conclusion suggests that Australia's diplomacy illustrates both the possibilities and the limits of middle power agency in a polarised regional order. Middle power diplomacy in this context is less about achieving independence and more about managing contradictions, which makes the Australian experience an important case study for other states navigating similar pressures.

*Former Faculty Member, Department of Political Science, Women's College, AMU, Aligarh. abparry.ps@amu.ac.in

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I. Introduction

The Indo-Pacific has emerged as the most strategically contested region of the twenty-first century. While the intensifying rivalry between the United States and China dominates regional geopolitics,¹ the story of this region cannot be reduced to great power competition alone. The most prominent characteristic of the Indo-Pacific order is the increasing role of middle powers - states that are neither as system-determining as the U.S. and China, nor insignificant, but whose geographic location, economic standing and diplomatic activism can shape outcomes in meaningful ways.² Middle powers exercise influence less through coercion and more through strategies of coalition-building, multilateral engagement, norm entrepreneurship and selective balancing.

While middle powers shape regional dynamics through coalitions and norm-setting, their agency must be situated within the overarching realities of great power politics. As Paul Kennedy argued in *The Rise and Fall of the Great Powers*, the distribution of material capabilities among major states has historically determined the structure of the international order.³ Although Kennedy's thesis of cyclical decline was later challenged by Jeremy Black, who emphasised the contingency of geopolitical shifts and the resilience of state power, both perspectives underscore that systemic outcomes are largely driven by the strategies and resources of great powers.⁴ John Mearsheimer's formulation of offensive realism further reinforces this by showing that great powers, compelled by the anarchic system, relentlessly pursue regional hegemony.⁵ Within the Indo-Pacific, the intensifying competition

¹Graham Allison, *Destined for War: Can America and China Escape Thucydides's Trap?* (Boston: Houghton Mifflin Harcourt, 2017).

²Andrew F. Cooper, Richard A. Higgott and Kim Richard Nossal, *Relocating Middle Powers: Australia and Canada in a Changing World Order* (Vancouver: UBC Press, 1993).; Mark Beeson and Chris Lee-Brown, "Middle Powers and the Changing Global Order," *Australian Journal of International Affairs* 70, no. 2 (2016): 132–50.

³Paul M. Kennedy, *The Rise and Fall of the Great Powers: Economic Change and Military Conflict from 1500 to 2000* (New York: Random House, 1987).

⁴Jeremy Black, *Great Powers and the Quest for Hegemony: The World Order since 1500* (New York/London: Routledge, 2008).

⁵John J. Mearsheimer, *The Tragedy of Great Power Politics* (New York: W. W. Norton & Company, 2001).

between the United States and China reflects precisely this logic, with both seeking to secure strategic primacy. Middle powers such as Australia, therefore operate in a structural environment dominated by these hegemonic contests, compelled to adapt their diplomacy within the constraints of great power rivalry rather than independently remaking the order.

Middle power diplomacy in the Indo-Pacific is exemplified in a variety of ways. Japan, once reluctant to assume a proactive security role, has in recent years shifted its posture with a new *National Security Strategy* while promoting the ‘Free and Open Indo-Pacific’ vision, a clear act of regional norm entrepreneurship.⁶ South Korea, traditionally cautious in its foreign policy, has launched its own Indo-Pacific Strategy, signalling a recalibration of its external priorities.⁷ Indonesia, though often reluctant to be categorised as a middle power, has shaped regional discourse by championing the Association of South East Asian Nations (ASEAN) Outlook on the Indo-Pacific.⁸ Collectively, these examples illustrate that middle powers are not passive actors caught between the giants, but active players attempting to adapt their roles in a shifting environment.

The idea of a ‘middle power moment’ that gained traction in the early 2010s reflected optimism about the capacity of such states to restructure international order through multilateralism and functional diplomacy.⁹ Initiatives such as Mexico, Indonesia, Korea, Turkey and Australia (MIKTA) and Kevin Rudd’s proposal for an Asia-Pacific Community highlighted this aspiration.¹⁰ Yet, a decade later, such projects have largely stalled or faded and the space for middle power diplomacy has been reshaped by the hardening of U.S.-China competition. Today, middle powers are compelled to recalibrate their diplomacy by investing

⁶Rory Medcalf, *Indo-Pacific Empire: China, America and the Contest for the World’s Pivotal Region* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2020).

⁷William T. Tow and Paul Kerr, *Australia’s Indo-Pacific Strategy: Security and Order in a Changing Region* (London: Routledge, 2022).

⁸Cheng-Chwee Kuik, “Middle Powers and the Shifting Dynamics of the Indo-Pacific,” *Asian Journal of Comparative Politics* 5, no. 4 (2020): 305–24.

⁹Andrew Carr, *Is Australia a Middle Power?* (Canberra: Australian National University Press, 2014).

¹⁰Kevin Rudd, “It’s Time to Build an Asia-Pacific Community,” *The Sydney Morning Herald*, June 5, 2008.

more in security partnerships, hedging¹¹ strategies and minilateral forums that tie them more closely to great power cores.¹²

Australia stands out as one of the most prominent middle powers in this landscape. Its experience captures both the opportunities and the dilemmas faced by second-tier states in a region sliding toward great power competition. On one hand, Australia has historically embraced the middle power identity, projecting influence through multilateral institutions, coalition-building and norm entrepreneurship.¹³ It played a role in initiatives ranging from Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC) to the Comprehensive and Progressive Agreement for Trans-Pacific Partnership (CPTPP), demonstrating its capacity to drive regional governance.¹⁴ On the other hand, the intensification of U.S.-China rivalry has forced Australia to recalibrate its diplomacy. Canberra's heavy reliance on China as a trading partner collides with its dependence on U.S. security guarantees, creating a structural tension between economic and security imperatives.¹⁵

This tension has been further complicated by Australia's shifting strategic preferences in recent years. The *Defence Strategic Review*¹⁶ and participation in U.S.-led minilateral forums such as Australia-United Kingdom-United States security partnership (AUKUS) and the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue (Quad) reflect a growing emphasis on

¹¹ In international relations, "hedging" refers to a strategy whereby states pursue contradictory policies of engagement and balancing simultaneously to manage uncertainty about the intentions and future behaviour of major powers. Unlike straightforward balancing, which seeks to counter a threatening state, or bandwagoning, which entails alignment with a dominant power, hedging combines cooperative economic and diplomatic ties with security measures designed to offset risks. This allows middle powers such as Australia to avoid making definitive choices between competing great powers while maintaining room for manoeuvre in a fluid strategic environment.

¹³ Allan Gyngell and Michael Wesley, *Making Australian Foreign Policy*, 2nd ed. (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2017).

¹⁴ Ibid.

¹⁵ Hugh White, *How to Defend Australia* (Melbourne: La Trobe University Press, 2019).

¹⁶ Australian Government, *Defence Strategic Review 2023* (Canberra: Commonwealth of Australia, 2023).

hard power and order-building, suggesting that Canberra, like other Indo-Pacific middle powers, is moving away from the more optimistic, multilateralist “middle power moment” of the early 2010s.¹⁷ Middle powers are no longer merely promoting broad-based institution-building; rather, they are increasingly hedging, balancing and investing in great power-led minilaterals to secure their national interests.¹⁸

To address this problem, the paper pursues three objectives: (i) to revisit theoretical debates on the concept of middle power diplomacy and situate Australia within them; (ii) to map the structural contradictions of Australia’s security and economic dependencies; and (iii) to assess whether diversification strategies through India, Japan, ASEAN and minilaterals such as the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue (Quad) enhance Canberra’s autonomy. The study argues that while Australia is indeed practising middle power diplomacy through diversification and coalition-building, its independence is significantly circumscribed by reliance on U.S. security guarantees and vulnerability to Chinese economic leverage.

II. Research Questions

This study seeks to examine the dynamics of Australia’s diplomacy within the broader theoretical framework of middle power behaviour, situating its foreign policy choices in relation to both structural imperatives and regional complexities. It interrogates the extent to which Australia can reconcile and sustain a balance between its security commitments—most prominently articulated through its alliance with the United States and its participation in arrangements such as AUKUS and the Quad—and its extensive economic partnerships, particularly with China, but also with other significant regional actors including India, Japan, and ASEAN. In this context, the research investigates the structural constraints and strategic opportunities that shape Australia’s pursuit of an autonomous middle power identity in the Indo-Pacific order. Finally, it considers whether Australia’s diplomatic strategy can be meaningfully conceptualised as a model of middle power balancing with potential relevance for other states navigating similar regional and systemic pressures.

The next section develops the theoretical framework on middle power diplomacy, drawing from the literature on international hierarchy, hedging strategies and minilateralism. The third section examines

¹⁷Andrew Carr, no. 9; William T. Tow and Paul Kerr, no. 7

¹⁸Cheng-Chwee Kuik, no. 8

Australia's economic and security dilemmas by analysing its relations with China and the United States. The fourth section explores Australia's engagement with other Indo-Pacific actors, especially India, Japan, ASEAN and Pacific Island states. The fifth section discusses the constraints that limit Australia's autonomy, ranging from domestic politics to structural dependence on major powers. The conclusion synthesises the findings and reflects on the broader implications of Australia's strategy for the future of middle power diplomacy in the Indo-Pacific.

III. Theoretical Framework: Rethinking Middle Power Diplomacy

The concept of the "middle power" has long been a contested yet enduring category in the study of international relations. It emerged during the Cold War as scholars sought to capture the role of states that were neither global superpowers nor marginal small states but nonetheless played meaningful roles in international order. Carsten Holbraad's seminal study traced the lineage of the idea to the nineteenth-century German notion of *Mittelmacht*, which described geographically and materially intermediate states that could balance or cooperate with great powers within the Concert of European system.¹⁹ For Holbraad, middle powers derive their identity primarily from positional and material traits: their intermediate location within a geopolitical hierarchy and their ability to leverage this position through diplomacy.²⁰

Building on this foundation, Robert Cox redefined middle powers in terms of their functional roles in global order.²¹ For Cox, these states did not necessarily engage in balancing against great powers but often acted as supportive stabilizers, providing mediatory functions and endorsing hegemonic structures that underpinned systemic stability. His formulation highlighted that middle powers should enjoy sufficient autonomy in shaping their foreign policy strategies while still aligning with great powers to sustain the rules-based system. In other words, middle powers are neither revisionist challengers nor passive followers but managerial actors that reinforce system-wide stability while pursuing their own interests.

¹⁹ Carsten Holbraad, "The Role of Middle Powers," *Cooperation and Conflict* 6, no. 2 (1971).

²⁰ *Ibid.*

²¹ Robert W. Cox, "Middlepowermanship, Japan and Future World Order," *International Journal* 44, no. 4 (1989): 823–862.

Andrew Cooper sought to rejuvenate middle power theory by expanding its definitional criteria.²² He argued that beyond material and positional features, middle powers could also be identified through normative and behavioural traits. Normatively, middle powers often portray themselves as responsible ‘good international citizens’ that invest in upholding multilateral institutions, international law and global norms. Behaviourally, they pursue conflict resolution and cooperative problem-solving, privileging multilateral and minilateral diplomacy over unilateral action. Cooper’s framework thus emphasised the identity politics of middle powers, portraying them as trustworthy partners that support a rules-based international order.

Despite the endurance of these traditional conceptions, the category of middle powers has faced persistent criticisms. One concern is the elasticity of the definition: because positional, normative and behavioural traits can be broadly applied, the term has often been stretched to include an overly wide range of states, from Canada, Australia and Japan to Turkey, Brazil and Saudi Arabia.²³ This definitional inflation risks stripping the category of analytical value. Another critique is that middle power theory historically adopted a globalist lens, classifying states as middle powers in general terms without sufficiently accounting for regional contexts. A state that functions as a middle power in the global arena may not occupy a similar role regionally and vice versa. For instance, Australia and Japan are often labelled as global middle powers, yet their activism through the Quad and AUKUS illustrates behaviour more akin to regional major powers, directly balancing China’s influence in the Indo-Pacific.²⁴

To address these limitations, recent scholarship has advanced more refined criteria for defining middle powers in the twenty-first century. This updated conceptualisation can be organised into four interlinked attributes:

First, positional traits remain central: middle powers must possess intermediate political, economic and military capabilities relative to both great powers and small states, while also demonstrating diplomatic

²² Andrew F. Cooper, *Niche Diplomacy: Middle Powers after the Cold War* (London: Macmillan, 1997).

²³ Matthew Stephen, “Concept and Role of Middle Powers during Global Rebalancing,” *Seton Hall Journal of Diplomacy and International Relations* 14, no. 2 (2013): 39–55.

²⁴ Allan Patience, “Imagining Middle Powers,” *Australian Journal of International Affairs* 68, no. 2 (2014): 210–29.

proficiency that allows them to ‘punch above their weight.’²⁵ Second, geographical embeddedness matters: middle powers operate within regions marked by sharp asymmetries of power and their influence derives from how effectively they leverage their location and resources to engage both neighbouring states and extra-regional actors.²⁶ Third, hierarchical contentment is essential: middle powers do not typically seek to overthrow the existing order but aim to maintain and steward the integrity of the rules-based system. By being ‘content’ with their rank, they avoid being perceived as revisionist challengers while carving space to advance their interests.²⁷ Finally, middle powers must demonstrate a foreign policy orientation rooted in liberal realism, that is, a realist acknowledgment of sovereignty, hierarchy and interstate competition, combined with liberal strategies of norm-setting, institution-building and coalition diplomacy.²⁸ Taken together, these attributes reposition middle powers as stewards of regional order rather than passive actors caught in the slipstream of great power politics. They use multilateralism and minilateralism to influence outcomes, employ normative appeals to legitimise their activism and balance pragmatically between great power blocs without fully aligning with or confronting them.

This theoretical framework is particularly relevant to the Indo-Pacific, where strategic rivalry between the United States and China has heightened pressures on states to choose sides. The role of middle powers in this context is neither trivial nor redundant: their strategies of hedging, coalition-building and rule promotion often determine whether the region gravitates toward multipolarity, bipolar confrontation, or some hybrid arrangement. Applying this framework to the case of Australia allows us to evaluate whether Canberra is successfully navigating these dynamics as a middle power steward of order, or whether it is increasingly constrained by the gravitational pull of U.S.-China rivalry.

²⁵ Matthew Stephen, no. 23

²⁶ Andrew F. Cooper and Emel Parlar Dal, “Positioning the Third Wave of Middle Power Diplomacy: Institutional Elevation, Practice Limitations,” in Bruce Gilley and Andrew O’Neil (eds.), *Middle Powers and the Rise of China* (London: Routledge, 2016), 126–45.

²⁷ Andrew F. Cooper, “Testing Middle Power Collective Action in a World of Diffuse Power,” *International Journal* 71, no. 4 (2016): 499–508.

²⁸ Stephen D. Krasner, *Sovereignty: Organized Hypocrisy* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1999).

IV. Australia's Strategic Dilemma: Security Alliances versus Economic Dependence

The theoretical debates around middle power diplomacy highlight the capacity of states with intermediate power to balance material constraints with normative and institutional activism. When applied to Australia, these debates are particularly illuminating, as Canberra faces one of the most complex strategic dilemmas in the Indo-Pacific. On the one hand, Australia has long relied on its alliance with the United States as the cornerstone of its national security strategy. This relationship, formalised through the Australia, New Zealand and the US (ANZUS) Treaty of 1951 and reinforced through successive defence white papers, provides Australia with access to advanced military technologies, intelligence-sharing arrangements and extended deterrence against potential adversaries. The U.S. alliance has not only guaranteed Australia's defence but also embedded it within a broader liberal order that emphasises freedom of navigation, open markets and rule-based governance.²⁹

On the other hand, Australia's economic prosperity has become deeply intertwined with China, which since the early 2000s has emerged as its largest trading partner. By 2019, over 32.6% of Australia's exports went to China, amounting to more than AUD 150 billion annually, dominated by iron ore, coal, liquefied natural gas and agricultural commodities.³⁰ The educational sector also became heavily reliant on Chinese students, who comprised nearly 40% of all international enrollments in Australian universities in 2019.³¹ This degree of dependence far exceeds Australia's exposure to any other single market, underlining the vulnerability of its economic model. This dual reliance, on the United States for security and on China for economic prosperity, has placed Australia in a uniquely precarious position, forcing it to navigate contradictory pressures from its two most important partners.

The risks of such dependence became apparent during recent political tensions. In 2020, after Canberra called for an international inquiry into the origins of COVID-19, Beijing responded with punitive trade

²⁹Nick Bisley, "Australia and the Rules-Based Order," *Australian Journal of International Affairs* 71, no. 1 (2017): 1–17.

³⁰Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade (DFAT), *Trade and Investment at a Glance 2020* (Canberra: Commonwealth of Australia, 2020).

³¹Universities Australia, *International Education Data 2019* (Canberra: Universities Australia, 2020).

measures, including tariffs of up to 80% on barley, bans on coal imports and restrictions on beef and wine.³² Although Australia weathered the storm due to sustained iron ore demand, these coercive actions revealed the fragility of its export base. The episode highlighted how China could weaponise economic leverage to influence Australian behaviour, forcing policymakers to reassess the costs of over-dependence.

From the perspective of middle power theory, this predicament reveals both the opportunities and limitations of Australia's diplomatic agency. In terms of positional traits, Australia's intermediate power status compels it to maximise its diplomatic reach through alliances and coalitions, since it cannot unilaterally deter or balance against China. Its geographical embeddedness in the Indo-Pacific further intensifies this dilemma, as the region constitutes the primary theatre of U.S.–China rivalry, exposing Australia to the direct consequences of strategic polarisation. At the same time, Australia's hierarchical contentment with the U.S.-led order shapes its foreign policy behaviour: rather than adopting a revisionist stance, Canberra has consistently sought to preserve and defend the liberal rules-based system in which its prosperity and security are embedded.³³ Yet this liberal realist orientation also forces Australia into an awkward balancing act—resisting Chinese coercion while avoiding outright economic decoupling.

The resulting strategy has often been described as one of hedging: Australia engages in deeper security integration with the United States through initiatives like the Force Posture Agreement and AUKUS, while simultaneously maintaining high-level diplomatic dialogues and selective economic partnerships with China. However, as China has increasingly used economic coercion, such as restrictions on Australian wine, coal and barley imports in response to political disagreements, Australia's room for manoeuvre as a middle power appears constrained.³⁴ The classical image of the middle power as a mediator or good international citizen thus collides with the realities of great power rivalry, raising a critical question: can Australia sustain a distinctive middle power role, or is it gradually being pushed into the orbit of its security guarantor at the expense of economic pragmatism?

³²Shiro Armstrong and Peter Drysdale, "Economic Coercion: China's Trade Sanctions against Australia," East Asian Bureau of Economic Research, Australian National University, 2021.

³³Allan Patience, no. 24

³⁴Rory Medcalf, no. 6

V. Australia's Hedging: Diversification through India, Japan, ASEAN and the Quad

Australia's hedging strategy is not merely discursive but increasingly quantifiable in economic and defence terms. The Australia–India Economic Cooperation and Trade Agreement (ECTA) illustrates this shift with measurable trade flows. By 2023, bilateral trade between India and Australia reached AUD 46.5 billion, a sharp rise compared to AUD 27.5 billion in 2021, with Indian imports of Australian coal, critical minerals and education services driving the surge. Under ECTA, tariffs on 96% of Indian exports to Australia and 85% of Australian exports to India were eliminated, representing an unprecedented degree of market opening between the two economies. The Australian Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade projects that the agreement will expand bilateral trade to over AUD 50 billion annually by 2030, giving Canberra its clearest alternative export corridor beyond China.³⁵

In the security domain, Canberra's partnership with Japan now includes measurable defence interoperability commitments. Defence spending has steadily increased, reaching 2.04% of GDP in 2022-23 (about AUD 48.7 billion), with portions allocated toward joint projects with Japan and the United States under trilateral frameworks.³⁶ The Japan–Australia Reciprocal Access Agreement (RAA) not only facilitates joint training but also signals readiness to coordinate responses to regional contingencies, as evidenced by the 2023 Exercise Talisman Sabre, which included large-scale Japanese participation for the first time.³⁷ This integration reflects how Australia translates middle-power stewardship into concrete operational cooperation.

The ASEAN partnership has likewise taken on measurable weight. ASEAN collectively accounted for 14.7% of Australia's total trade in goods and services in 2022, making the bloc Australia's second-largest trading partner after China.³⁸ The Comprehensive Strategic Partnership (CSP) thus anchors not only normative commitments to ASEAN centrality but also pragmatic diversification: education exports to

³⁵DFAT, *Australia's Trade in Goods and Services 2022* (Canberra: DFAT, 2023).; Harsh V. Singh, "India–Australia Economic Cooperation and Trade Agreement: A New Milestone," *Observer Research Foundation Issue Brief*, February 2023.

³⁶ Australian Government, *Defence White Paper 2016* (Canberra: Department of Defence, 2016).

³⁷Rory Medcalf, no. 6

³⁸DFAT, no. 30.

Southeast Asia alone were worth over AUD 6 billion in 2022, while Australian investments in digital and green infrastructure projects under the CSP are projected to grow steadily.³⁹ These figures underline the economic rationale behind Canberra's institutional engagement with ASEAN.

Finally, the Quad provides both symbolic and resource-based dividends. Australia has already pledged USD 212 million (AUD 300 million) toward Quad initiatives in areas such as regional health security, cyber capacity building and maritime domain awareness.⁴⁰ This level of investment reflects Canberra's attempt to turn minilateral frameworks into platforms that distribute the costs of public goods provision across partners. The Quad also expands the scope of middle-power diplomacy by enabling Australia to pool resources with other like-minded states while avoiding the exclusivity of formal alliance structures.⁴¹

What these empirical markers reveal is the asymmetry of progress: while trade with India and ASEAN is expanding, China still accounted for nearly 30% of Australia's total trade in 2022 (AUD 287 billion), underscoring the persistence of economic vulnerability.⁴² Similarly, while defence diversification through Japan and the Quad is deepening, Canberra remains structurally reliant on U.S. intelligence, nuclear submarine technology (AUKUS) and extended deterrence guarantees.⁴³ Hence, Australia's hedging, though substantive, remains a balancing act that partially mitigates but does not erase the contradictions of asymmetric interdependence. In theoretical terms, this evidence confirms that middle powers such as Australia pursue hedging as both positional strategy and liberal-realist stewardship, but their structural autonomy remains constrained by enduring economic and security asymmetries.

³⁹ASEAN Secretariat, *ASEAN Statistical Yearbook 2022* (Jakarta: ASEAN, 2022).

⁴⁰Quad Leaders, "Quad Joint Statement," Tokyo, May 2022,

⁴¹William T. Tow and Douglas Stuart, "The Quad and Minilateral Security in the Indo-Pacific," *Strategic Studies Quarterly* 15, no. 2 (2021): 89–113.

⁴²Lowy Institute, *Asia Power Index 2023* (Sydney: Lowy Institute, 2023).

⁴³ Hugh White, "Sleepwalk to War: Australia's Unthinking Alliance with America," *Quarterly Essay* 87 (Melbourne: Black Inc., 2023).

VI. Middle Power Diplomacy and Strategic Autonomy: Assessing Australia's Options

The preceding discussion has highlighted the structural contradiction in Australia's external relations: its dependence on the United States for security and on China for economic prosperity. This duality reflects the classic predicament of a middle power operating in an environment shaped by great power rivalry. In this section, the article evaluates whether Australia's diplomatic manoeuvres, through diversification, unilateralism and coalition-building, genuinely provide it with strategic autonomy, or whether these efforts remain constrained by structural asymmetries.

VII. Middle Power Agency and Its Limits

The notion of middle power diplomacy presumes that states with limited material capabilities can nevertheless exercise disproportionate influence by leveraging soft power, multilateral activism and coalition politics.⁴⁴ Australia has historically embodied this model, playing norm-entrepreneurial roles in the establishment of APEC and the Cairns Group in agricultural trade negotiations. Yet, as scholars of middle power theory have noted, agency is often conditional upon the permissive environment created by great power consensus or benign rivalry.⁴⁵ In the present Indo-Pacific, the intensification of U.S.–China competition has curtailed such space, compelling middle powers to adapt their diplomacy toward risk management and strategic hedging.

Australia's embrace of the Quad, AUKUS and Comprehensive Strategic Partnerships with India and Japan illustrate this shift from broad-based institution-building toward selective security and economic alignments. These moves suggest agency, but one tempered by the structural reality of dependence on U.S. defence commitments and Chinese trade flows. The critical question is whether these hedging strategies genuinely expand autonomy or merely delay hard choices between Washington and Beijing.

VIII. Hedging versus Bandwagoning

Australia's foreign policy behaviour has been widely interpreted as a form of hedging, defined as the pursuit of policies that avoid full

⁴⁴Andrew F. Cooper, Richard A. Higgott and Kim Richard Nossal, no 2

⁴⁵Eduard Jordaan, "The Concept of a Middle Power in International Relations: Distinguishing between Emerging and Traditional Middle Powers," *Politikon* (Pretoria: South African Association of Political Studies, 2003).

alignment with one great power while simultaneously seeking to mitigate risks posed by others.⁴⁶ Hedging typically combines contradictory elements: engagement with China on trade, while aligning more closely with the U.S. and its allies on security. Empirically, Canberra exemplifies this dual-track approach. Even amid the diplomatic freeze of 2020–22, when Beijing imposed tariffs on Australian wine, barley and coal, Canberra avoided outright economic decoupling and trade in iron ore continued to underpin the relationship.⁴⁷ At the same time, Australia deepened defence cooperation with Washington and Tokyo, underscored by the AUKUS agreement to acquire nuclear-powered submarines.

Some analysts, however, question whether Australia has moved beyond hedging into a de facto bandwagoning with the U.S.⁴⁸ AUKUS, with its explicit focus on advanced military interoperability, suggests a strategic bet on Washington's long-term regional presence. From this perspective, hedging may no longer be a tenable description, as Australia's security commitments have decisively tilted toward the U.S., leaving little room for genuine equidistance.

IX. Comparative Middle Power Experiences

Placing Australia in comparative perspective illuminates both the distinctiveness and the limits of its strategy. South Korea, another U.S. ally deeply integrated with the Chinese economy, has pursued a similar balancing act, but with greater reluctance to embrace overt security coalitions like the Quad, for fear of antagonising Beijing.⁴⁹ Canada, traditionally cast as a middle power, faces its own dilemma of over-dependence on the U.S. market, underscoring how geographic and

⁴⁶ Cheng-Chwee Kuik, "The Essence of Hedging: Malaysia and Singapore's Response to a Rising China," *Contemporary Southeast Asia* 30, no. 2 (2008): 159–85.

⁴⁷ Shiro Armstrong and Peter Drysdale, "Economic Coercion: China's Trade Sanctions against Australia," East Asian Bureau of Economic Research, Australian National University, 2021.

⁴⁸ Hugh White, *Without America: Australia's Future in the New Asia* (Melbourne: Black Inc., 2017).

⁴⁹ Sook-Jong Lee, "South Korea between the United States and China: Hedging in an Age of Great Power Competition," *Asian Perspective* 44, no. 2 (2020): 217–44.

economic asymmetry constrain middle power autonomy.⁵⁰ ASEAN states, meanwhile, engage in “omni-enmeshment,” deliberately tying themselves into multiple frameworks to avoid binary choices.⁵¹ Compared to these cases, Australia appears more willing to accept strategic risks vis-à-vis China, leaning into the U.S. alliance system in a way that arguably reduces its space for manoeuvre.

This brings us to the paradox of Australia’s middle power diplomacy: its efforts to secure greater strategic autonomy may, paradoxically, deepen dependence on the U.S. alliance system. The pursuit of nuclear-powered submarines under AUKUS, for instance, ties Australia into decades-long reliance on U.S. and U.K. technology, training and operational integration.⁵² Far from enhancing autonomy, such commitments may reduce Canberra’s independent decision-making capacity in moments of crisis.

On the economic front, diversification into India, Japan and ASEAN offers potential, but it is unlikely to fully replace the scale of the Chinese market in the near term. Even with recent trade agreements, China continues to account for roughly one-third of Australia’s exports, particularly in critical commodities like iron ore.⁵³ This asymmetric interdependence constrains Canberra’s freedom of action: while it can resist coercion in the short term, its structural vulnerability remains.

X. Assessing Strategic Options

Three broad scenarios emerge from this analysis. First, Australia could double down on U.S. alignment, accepting reduced autonomy in exchange for security guarantees. Second, it could attempt to revive a more classic middle power role by investing in inclusive regional institutions and positioning itself as a bridge-builder. Third, it could pursue deeper diversification of trade and defence partners to reduce dependence on any single power bloc. Each scenario carries trade-offs: alignment maximises security but limits autonomy, bridge-building restores normative influence but risks irrelevance in a polarised region

⁵⁰Adam Chapnick, “The Middle Power,” *Canadian Foreign Policy Journal* 7, no. 2 (1999): 73–82.

⁵¹Amitav Acharya, *Constructing a Security Community in Southeast Asia: ASEAN and the Problem of Regional Order*, 2nd ed. (London: Routledge, 2014).

⁵²Rory Medcalf, “Australia, Japan and Exercise Talisman Sabre 2023,” commentary, Lowy Institute, July 2021.

⁵³DFAT, no. 30

and diversification offers resilience but requires sustained political and economic investment.

Ultimately, Australia illustrates the dilemmas of middle power diplomacy in the Indo-Pacific: agency exists, but it is structurally bounded. Rather than a free choice, Canberra's strategy is one of navigating constraints, where every option involves entanglement with great power politics. The Australian case thus provides a textbook example of how middle powers in the Indo-Pacific seek to manoeuvre within the cracks of great power rivalry, with limited but not negligible room for independent action.

XI. Middle Power Diplomacy in Comparative Perspective: Australia, South Korea, Canada and ASEAN

To fully understand whether Australia is successfully navigating its middle power role in the Indo-Pacific, it is useful to place its strategy in comparative context with other states that confront similar structural dilemmas. Middle power diplomacy is rarely pursued in isolation; rather, it emerges from the interlocking pressures of economic dependence, security guarantees and regional institutional engagement. By contrasting Australia's position with South Korea, Canada and ASEAN, one can identify both the unique features of its strategic balancing and the broader patterns of asymmetric interdependence that shape middle power options globally.

Australia's trade dependence on China has become one of the most pronounced cases of asymmetric interdependence. In 2022, approximately 30-35 percent of Australia's total exports were directed to China, dominated by iron ore, coal, LNG, agricultural products and education services.⁵⁴ The scale of dependence means that any disruption in this relationship has immediate consequences for Australia's economy. The episode following Canberra's call for an independent COVID-19 origins inquiry in 2020, which led to Beijing imposing punitive tariffs and restrictions on Australian wine, barley, beef and coal, exposed the vulnerability inherent in this arrangement.⁵⁵

South Korea presents a similar, though sectorally distinct, pattern of dependence. Roughly 25% of its exports go to China, primarily in

⁵⁴ DFAT, no. 30

⁵⁵ Geoff Raby, "China's Trade Retaliation and Australia's Vulnerability," *Australian Journal of International Affairs* 74, no. 5 (2020): 529–36.

electronics, semiconductors and intermediate goods.⁵⁶ When Seoul agreed to host the U.S. ‘Thermal High Altitude Areal Defence’ (THAAD) system in 2016, Beijing retaliated through informal sanctions targeting South Korean consumer goods, tourism and cultural products, an episode that closely parallels Australia’s experience of economic coercion.⁵⁷

Canada, in contrast, illustrates the other side of asymmetric interdependence. Nearly 75% of Canadian exports go to the United States, a level of concentration far greater than Australia’s or South Korea’s exposure to China.⁵⁸ Here, the asymmetry lies not with China but with the U.S., reflecting the structural reality of being a middle power in the North American context.

ASEAN’s collective position is somewhat different. The bloc has attempted to avoid over-dependence on a single partner through diversified ties, yet China has emerged as ASEAN’s largest trading partner since 2009, with trade reaching US\$669 billion in 2021, compared to US\$362 billion with the United States.⁵⁹ While no single ASEAN state faces exposure as acute as Australia or South Korea, the collective trade profile demonstrates a similar structural dilemma in balancing between Beijing and Washington.

XII. Security Dependence and Alliance Commitments

Australia’s security dependence on the United States has been a defining feature of its foreign policy since the ANZUS Treaty of 1951, which enshrined the U.S. as Canberra’s ultimate security guarantor. This dependence has deepened over time, especially with the AUKUS agreement of 2021, which commits Australia to acquiring nuclear-powered submarines and advanced U.S.-UK defence technologies. While AUKUS significantly upgrades Australia’s military capacity, it also underscores Canberra’s reliance on U.S. defence technology, intelligence sharing and operational integration.⁶⁰

⁵⁶Korea International Trade Association (KITA), *Korea’s Trade Statistics 2022* (Seoul: KITA, 2022).

⁵⁷Sook-Jong Lee, “Hedging in South Korea’s Foreign Policy,” *Journal of Contemporary Asia* 49, no. 5 (2019): 792–810.

⁵⁸Statistics Canada, *Canada’s International Merchandise Trade 2022* (Ottawa: Statistics Canada, 2022).

⁵⁹ASEAN Secretariat, no. 39

⁶⁰Rory Medcalf, no. 52

South Korea's position mirrors this in important respects. Bound by the U.S.-ROK Mutual Defence Treaty of 1953, South Korea depends on the presence of approximately 28,500 U.S. troops stationed on its soil for deterrence against North Korea and broader regional threats.⁶¹ However, unlike Australia, which faces no immediate territorial threat, South Korea's security dependence is sharpened by its direct confrontation with Pyongyang, leaving it little space for independent manoeuvring.

Canada's security orientation is more regionally insulated but equally tied to Washington. As a founding member of NATO and participant in NORAD, Canada's defence architecture is deeply embedded within U.S.-led systems.⁶² Yet the difference lies in geography: Canada is buffered from immediate conflict zones, giving it more leeway to exercise normative middle power diplomacy, particularly in peacekeeping and multilateral fora.

ASEAN, finally, lacks a formal collective defence alliance comparable to ANZUS or NATO. Instead, the Treaty of Amity and Cooperation (TAC) and the ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF) emphasise dialogue, non-interference and conflict prevention. While individual ASEAN states (e.g., the Philippines with the U.S. Mutual Defence Treaty) have bilateral security commitments, the bloc as a whole relies on institutional balancing rather than external guarantees.⁶³

The comparative evidence illustrates that Australia's predicament is not unique but a variant of a broader structural pattern where middle powers confront tensions between economic and security imperatives. In both Australia and South Korea, heavy trade dependence on China collides with reliance on the U.S. for security guarantees. Canada faces the opposite asymmetry, economic and security dependence converging on the United States. ASEAN demonstrates collective hedging through diversification, though China's centrality to its trade makes it vulnerable to shifts in great power competition.

What distinguishes Australia is the sharpness of the contradiction. Its economic lifeline lies with a state increasingly cast as its principal security challenge, while its security lifeline lies with a state increasingly embroiled in rivalry with that economic partner. This

⁶¹Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS), *The U.S.–South Korea Alliance: Facts and Figures* (Washington, DC: CSIS, 2022).

⁶² James Fergusson, "NORAD and Canadian Defense Policy," *Canadian Foreign Policy Journal* 27, no. 2 (2021): 186–200.

⁶³ Amitav Acharya, no. 51

“double dependence” represents a textbook case of asymmetric interdependence.⁶⁴ The empirical evidence suggests that while Australia has sought to mitigate its vulnerabilities through diversification, deepening ties with Japan, India and ASEAN via the Quad and Comprehensive Strategic Partnerships, it remains structurally constrained. The comparison underscores that middle power diplomacy offers agency, but agency is always mediated by the systemic pressures of great power competition.

Table 1: Comparative Economic and Security Dependence of Selected Middle Powers (2021–22)

Country	GDP (Nominal, USD Trillion)	Top Trading Partner	Exports to China (% of total)	Exports to U.S. (% of total)	Defence Spending (USD Billion)	Primary Security Alliance/Framework
Australia	1.55	China	34%	5%	38–40	ANZUS, AUKUS, Quad
South Korea	1.80	China	25%	15%	50	U.S.–ROK Mutual Defence Treaty
Canada	2.20	United States	4%	75%	26	NATO, NORAD
ASEAN (collective)	3.3 (approx.)	China	21%	10%	~43 (collective est.)	ASEAN Treaty of Amity & Cooperation (TAC)

Source: Compiled by the author using data from International Monetary Fund (IMF, 2022), World Bank (2022), Stockholm International Peace Research Institute (SIPRI, 2022), World Trade Organization (WTO, 2022) and relevant government reports.

⁶⁴ Robert O. Keohane and Joseph S. Nye, *Power and Interdependence: World Politics in Transition* (Boston: Little, Brown, 1977).

XIII. Conclusion

This study set out to investigate whether Australia is successfully exercising middle power diplomacy in the Indo-Pacific, or whether its agency remains circumscribed by the structural imperatives of great power politics. The analysis has demonstrated that Australia occupies a paradoxical strategic position: it is deeply enmeshed in the U.S.-led security architecture, while simultaneously economically dependent on China, its largest trading partner. This structural contradiction exemplifies what Keohane and Nye describe as ‘asymmetric interdependence’, where the very benefits of integration create vulnerabilities that limit strategic freedom.⁶⁵ Australia’s security commitments, most visibly institutionalised through ANZUS and AUKUS, ensure access to advanced military technology and intelligence sharing, but they also bind Canberra tightly to Washington’s strategic calculus. On the other hand, the reliance on Chinese markets for exports such as iron ore, coal and higher education underscores how prosperity remains contingent on stable economic ties with a geopolitical rival, a vulnerability that was laid bare during the post-COVID trade frictions.

Yet, to characterise Australia purely as a ‘dependent’ actor would overlook the agency it exercises through middle power diplomacy. Successive governments have invested in strategies of diversification and coalition-building designed to reduce the risks of over-dependence. The strengthening of Comprehensive Strategic Partnerships with India and Japan, active participation in the Quad and engagement with ASEAN-led institutions all signal a deliberate attempt to craft a multi-vector foreign policy that both balances against and engages with competing great powers. This posture aligns with the classical traits of middle power diplomacy, support for multilateralism, coalition-building on issue-specific agendas and efforts to uphold a rules-based order. Importantly, these moves reflect not only hedging against uncertainty but also a normative aspiration to reinforce Australia’s international identity as a constructive regional stabiliser.

Nevertheless, the constraints remain profound. Australia’s material capabilities, while significant relative to smaller states, are insufficient to underwrite an autonomous strategic posture. Its security continues to hinge on extended deterrence provided by the United States and its economic diversification, while progressing, cannot easily offset the gravitational pull of the Chinese market in the near term. This

⁶⁵ Ibid.

underscores a central finding of the paper: Australia's middle power diplomacy is simultaneously real and limited. It is real in that Canberra actively seeks to navigate the turbulent waters of Indo-Pacific geopolitics through diversification, coalition-building and multilateral engagement. It is limited because the structural conditions of great power competition constrain the extent to which such strategies can deliver full autonomy.

The broader implication of this research is that middle power diplomacy in the Indo-Pacific is best understood not as an escape from dependency but as a practice of managing contradictions. For Australia, this involves sustaining credibility as a reliable ally of the United States while also asserting itself as an independent actor within multilateral frameworks. The balancing act is delicate: too much alignment risks entrapment in U.S. great power competition with China, while excessive accommodation of China risks undermining security partnerships and domestic political legitimacy.

Looking forward, several policy directions emerge. First, accelerating economic diversification remains essential. Deepening trade and investment ties with India, ASEAN and Europe could incrementally reduce vulnerability to Chinese economic coercion. Second, strengthening leadership in the Pacific Islands would allow Australia to consolidate influence in a subregion where middle powers can exert disproportionate impact, thereby reinforcing its diplomatic identity. Third, prioritising issue-based cooperation on non-traditional security challenges such as climate change, cyber governance and health security could allow Canberra to project middle power leadership in domains less susceptible to zero-sum geopolitics. Finally, enhancing domestic resilience, by building societal consensus on foreign policy objectives and reducing polarised narratives about China, will be critical to sustaining coherent diplomacy.

While this study has highlighted the dilemmas and opportunities inherent in Australia's middle power diplomacy, several unresolved issues remain that complicate a definitive assessment of its strategic trajectory. First, the durability of Australia's current hedging strategy remains uncertain in the face of intensifying U.S.–China rivalry. As the Indo-Pacific security order becomes increasingly polarised, the scope for middle powers to exercise flexible diplomacy may shrink, raising questions about the long-term sustainability of diversification and coalition-building strategies. The structural contradiction between security dependence on the United States and economic reliance on China is likely to deepen rather than dissipate, suggesting that

Australia's diplomatic manoeuvrability could be progressively constrained.

Second, the domestic political dimension of foreign policy remains under-explored. Although bipartisan consensus has broadly underpinned Australia's Indo-Pacific orientation, growing public debate on issues such as Chinese influence, defence spending and climate diplomacy reveals potential fissures. How shifts in domestic political leadership, public opinion, or elite consensus shape the contours of Australia's middle power diplomacy is a question deserving closer scrutiny.

Third, the normative dimension of Australia's foreign policy, its commitment to promoting a 'rules-based order', requires further critical examination. While Canberra rhetorically champions multilateralism and international law, its alignment with U.S. strategic preferences, such as AUKUS, sometimes places it at odds with broader regional sensitivities, especially among ASEAN states wary of great power blocs. Whether Australia can reconcile its normative commitments with the imperatives of alliance politics remains an unresolved tension.

Finally, the scope of middle power diplomacy itself demands re-theorisation in light of emerging challenges. Traditional conceptualisations focus on coalition-building, mediation and support for multilateralism. Yet, as new domains of contestation such as cyber security, artificial intelligence governance and climate change gain salience, the question arises as to whether middle powers like Australia can carve out niches of influence in these spheres, or whether they remain overshadowed by great power competition.